

Subir Sachdev
Publications not on arXiv.org

Publications in refereed journals

1. Atom in a Damped Cavity by S. Sachdev, Physical Review A **29**, 2627 (1983); [DOI](#).
2. Crystalline and Fluid Order on a Random Topography by S. Sachdev and D. R. Nelson, Journal of Physics: Solid State C **17**, 5473 (1984); [DOI](#).
3. Theory of the Structure Factor of Metallic Glasses, S. Sachdev and D. R. Nelson, Physical Review Letters **53**, 1947 (1984); [DOI](#).
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5. Incommensurate Icosahedral Density Waves in Rapidly Cooled Metals, D. R. Nelson and S. Sachdev, Physical Review B **32**, 689, (1985); [DOI](#).
6. Statistical Mechanics of Pentagonal and Icosahedral Order in Dense Liquids, S. Sachdev and D. R. Nelson, Physical Review B **32**, 1480 (1985); [DOI](#).
7. Order in Metallic Glasses and Icosahedral Crystals, S. Sachdev and D. R. Nelson, Physical Review B **32**, 4592 (1985); [DOI](#).
8. Viscous Relaxation in Metallic Glasses, S. Sachdev, Physical Review B **33**, 6395 (1986); [DOI](#).
9. Excited States and the metal-insulator transition in monovalent systems by R. N. Bhatt and S. Sachdev, Physical Review B **34**, 3520, (1986); [DOI](#).
10. Electron Spin Resonance in Insulating Doped Semiconductors by S. Sachdev and R. N. Bhatt, Physical Review B **34**, 4898 (1986); [DOI](#).
11. Electron Spin Resonance in Disordered Metals by S. Sachdev, Physical Review B **34**, 6049 (1986); [DOI](#).
12. Spin Dynamics of Nearly Localized Electrons by M. A. Paalanen, S. Sachdev, R. N. Bhatt and A. E. Ruckenstein, Physical Review Letters **57**, 2061 (1986); [DOI](#).
13. Spin Dynamics Across the Metal-Insulator Transition, by S. Sachdev and R. N. Bhatt, Journal of Applied Physics **61**, 4366 (1987) [DOI](#).
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17. Magnetic Properties Across the Metal-Insulator Transition, by S. Sachdev, R. N. Bhatt and M. A. Paalanen, *Journal of Applied Physics* **63**, 4285 (1988); [DOI](#).
18. Superconductivity of Itinerant Electrons coupled to Spin Chains by S. Sachdev and R. Shankar, *Physical Review B* **38**, 826 (1988); [DOI](#).
19. Thermodynamic Behavior near a Metal-Insulator Transition by M. A. Paalanen, J. Graebner, S. Sachdev and R. N. Bhatt, *Physical Review Letters* **61**, 597, (1988); [DOI](#).
20. Local Moments near the Metal-Insulator Transition, by S. Sachdev. *Physical Review B* **39**, 5297 (1989); [DOI](#).
21. Hole motion in a Quantum Neel State, by S. Sachdev, *Physical Review B* **39**, 12232 (1989); [DOI](#).
22. Some Features of the Phase Diagram of $SU(N)$ Antiferromagnets on a Square Lattice, by N. Read and S. Sachdev, *Nucl Phys. B* **316**, 609 (1989); [DOI](#).
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24. Effective Field Theory of Local Moment Formation in Disordered Metals, by M. Milovanović, S. Sachdev and R.N. Bhatt, *Physical Review Letters* **63**, 82 (1989); [DOI](#).
25. Sine-Gordon theory of the non-Néel phase of two-dimensional quantum antiferromagnets, by W. Zheng and S. Sachdev, *Physical Review B* **40**, 2704 (1989); [DOI](#).
26. Spin-Peierls ground states of the quantum dimer model: a finite size study, by S. Sachdev, *Physical Review B* **40**, 5204 (1989); [DOI](#).
27. Large N limit of the square lattice $t-J$ model at $1/4$ and other filling fractions, by S. Sachdev, *Physical Review B* **41**, 4502 (1990); [DOI](#).
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30. Conservation laws, anisotropy and “self-organized criticality” in noisy non-equilibrium systems, by G. Grinstein, D. H. Lee, and S. Sachdev, *Physical Review Letters* **64**, 1927 (1990); [DOI](#).
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33. Large N expansion for frustrated quantum antiferromagnets, by N. Read and S. Sachdev, *Physical Review Letters*, **66**, 1773 (1991); [DOI](#).
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35. RVB and odd Z_2 spin liquids, S. Sachdev, notes dated July 30, 1990; [DOI](#).
36. Pairing in two dimensions: a systematic approach, by S. Sachdev and Z. Wang, *Physical Review B* **43**, 10229 (1991); [DOI](#).
37. Spontaneous alignment of frustrated bonds in an anisotropic, three dimensional Ising model, by R. Jalabert and S. Sachdev, *Physical Review B* **44**, 686 (1991); [DOI](#).
38. Stable hc/e vortices in a gauge theory of superconductivity in strongly correlated electronic systems. by S. Sachdev, *Physical Review B* **45**, 389 (1992); [DOI](#).
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40. The kagomé and triangular lattice Heisenberg antiferromagnets: ordering from quantum fluctuations and quantum-disordered ground states with unconfined bosonic spinons, by S. Sachdev, *Physical Review B* **45**, 12377 (1992); [DOI](#).

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1. Order and Frustration on a Random Topography by S. Sachdev and D. R. Nelson in *Applications of Field Theory to Statistical Mechanics*, Proceedings, Sitges Spain 1984, edited by L. Garrido, Springer-Verlag, Berlin 1985; [DOI](#).
2. Icosahedral Order in undercooled liquids and metallic glasses by D.R. Nelson and S. Sachdev in *Proceedings of the Workshop on Amorphous Metals and Semiconductors*, May 1985, edited by P. Haasen and R. Jaffe, Acta Metallurgica; [Weblink](#); [DOI](#).
3. Frustration and Order in Rapidly Cooled Metals by S. Sachdev, Proceedings of the NATO Advanced Research Workshop on Incommensurate Materials, July 1986; [DOI](#).
4. Electron Spin Resonance in Si:P near the metal-insulator transition by M. A. Paalanen, S. Sachdev and R. N. Bhatt, 18th International Conference on The Physics of Semiconductors, edited by Olof Engstrom, World Scientific, Singapore (1986); [DOI](#).

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6. Nature of the disordered phase of low dimensional quantum antiferromagnets, by S. Sachdev; lectures presented at the Winter School on Disorder and Correlation effects in metals, Puri, India, January 1989, and published in “Electronic Correlation and Disorder Effects in Metals” edited by S. N. Behera, World Scientific, Singapore; [DOI](#).
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8. Icosahedral ordering in supercooled liquids and metallic glasses, in *Bond Orientational Order in Condensed Matter Systems*, edited by K. J. Strandburg, Springer-Verlag, New York, 1992; [DOI](#).
9. Stable hc/e vortices in superconductors with spin-charge separation, International Journal of Modern Physics B **6**, 509 (1992); [DOI](#).
10. Spin glasses enter the quantum regime by S. Sachdev, Physics World, **7**, No. 10, 25 (October 1994); [DOI](#).
11. Landau theory of quantum spin glasses of rotors and Ising spins, N. Read and S. Sachdev, Nuclear Physics B – Proceedings Supplements, **45A**, 38 (1996); [DOI](#).
12. Finite temperature correlations of the Ising chain in a transverse field, by S. Sachdev, proceedings of the Symposium on “Exactly Soluble Models in Statistical Mechanics: Historical perspectives and current status”, March 30-31, 1996, Northeastern University, C. King and F. Y. Wu eds, International Journal of Modern Physics B **11**, 57 (1997); [DOI](#).
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15. Order and quantum phase transitions in the cuprate superconductors, by S. Sachdev, Solid State Communications **127**, 169 (2003), Proceedings of the Euroconference on Quantum phases at the nanoscale, Erice, Italy, 15-20 July 2002; [DOI](#).
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18. Quantum Phase Transitions, Encyclopedia of Mathematical Physics, eds. J.-P. Francoise, G.L. Naber and Tsou S.T., **4**, 289 (2006), Oxford: Elsevier; [Weblink](#); [DOI](#).
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